

Universitat Oberta
de Catalunya

Pathways to openness in Networked Learning research: The case of Open Data

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Workshop
Networked Learning Conference 2018
Zagreb, 14-16 May

Índex

[#ODNLC18 Folder](#)

Social Media: #ODNLC18

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01 On Open Science

[Photo Credit: Virginia Sea Grant via Flickr \(CC-BY 2.0\)](#)

01.1 Definitions & Policy Context

Open Science

Leveraging new,
technology
enhanced practices
and instruments

“There is no philosophy or unified solution advanced by Open Science advocates” (Fecher & Friesike, 2014)

- Fight against:
 - Cost barriers to accessing scientific research
 - High failure rates of replications studies
 - Publication bias
- Digital Science at Horizon 2020 (DG Connect, EU Commission, 2013)
- Implementation Roadmap for the European Science Cloud (2018)

01.2 Definitions & Policy Context

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01.3 Open Science

Remember!
**Responsible
Research &
Innovation**

01.4 Definitions & Policy Context

Open Data

...Still travelling from
the promise to the
actual practices

- One of the grand challenges of **data-intensive science** is to facilitate knowledge discovery by **assisting humans and machines in their discovery of, access to, integration and analysis** of, task-appropriate scientific data and their associated algorithms and workflows (The FAIR Data Principles, 2014).
- Open Data is **research data** that is **freely available** on the internet permitting any user to **download, copy, analyse, re-process**, pass to **software or use** for any other purpose **without financial, legal, or technical barriers** other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself (SPARC, n.d.)

01.5 Where is Open Data?

The screenshot shows the OpenAIRE website interface. At the top left is the OpenAIRE logo. To its right is a navigation menu with links for PARTICIPATE, SEARCH, MONITOR, SUPPORT, and OPEN ACCESS. Below the navigation is a banner image of a blue pen. On the left side of the page, there is a white box titled "Open Science in practice in FP9" containing text about OpenAIRE's recommendations and a "READ MORE" button. The main content area consists of a 2x2 grid of white cards with blue borders, each representing a stakeholder group: RESEARCHERS, DATA PROVIDERS, RESEARCH ADMINS, and FUNDERS. Each card contains a brief description of their role and how to use Open Access services.

RESEARCH

The EU Portal OpenAire:

<https://www.openaire.eu/>

Open Data: Repositories or ASNs?

- Figshare: <https://figshare.com/>
- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>
- Mendeley Data: <https://data.mendeley.com/>
- Harvard Dataverse: <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/>
- UK Data Service: Qualitative Data - <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/get-data/other-providers/qualitative/international>
- Open Data at Researchgate: [Researcher Profile/Contributions/Datasets](https://www.researchgate.net/profile/contributions/datasets)

A specific portal for Online Learning:
LearnSphere - <http://learnsphere.org/>

02

Open Data in EdTech

[Photo Credit: Justgrimes via Flickr \(CC-BY 2.0\)](#)

02.1 Open Data in Education Activities & Professional Development Issues

Open Data can be also found in Open Government activities

02.3 My trip into Open Data in EdTech

Selected Cases

02.4 My trip into Open Data in EdTech

Research Topics

Level of Analysis

Methodological Approach

02.5 My trip into Open Data in EdTech

Type of Files supporting Datasets

FAIR principles & Sharing Practices (Downloads)

02.6 My trip into Open Data in EdTech

Reflections

There is so much to do!

- The Portals report all sort of research resources and Open Datasets on the issue are not easy to find.
- The complexity and multilayered field of Educational Research is reflected on the type of data.
- Very little qualitative data shared.
- Restricted access to interesting data.
- Data shared regards very specific cases.
- ...Researchers and EdTech experts and practitioners need to approach to data critically and throughour a RRI scheme. Data Literacy is needed!

03

Resources & Activities

[Photo Credit: Daniel Foster via Flickr \(CC-BY 2.0\)](#)

03.1 This Workshop

My Data Practices

A questionnaire to explore
your knowledge and
practices

[Questionnaire](#)

03.2 This Workshop

My Force Map

Exploring the forces driving professional learning for change in your contexts of practice.

[MyForceMap](#)

03.3 Further resources

Self-paced learning

- OPENAIRE:
[Instructions for Researchers - How to Share Data - FOSTER/OpenAIRE at OpenCon](#)
- EUDAT – Cases of Open Data -
<https://www.eudat.eu/use-cases>
- Some TEDx Talks
 - [The future of our cities and towns lies in... Open Data | Laurenellen McCann | TEDxMidAtlantic](#)
 - [Open data and the quest for a just digital future | Marcel Salathé | TEDxLausanne](#)
 - [Open data changes lives | Jeanne Holm | TEDxUCLA](#)
 - [Open Data - Searching for the right questions | Boyan Yurukov | TEDxBG](#)

03.4 Further Resources

Self-paced learning, Training & Open Data Activism

- Project FOSTER – Resources: <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/resources>
- The Open Data Institute – Courses and training <https://theodi.org/service/courses-and-training/>
- ZENODO Research Data Management (RDM) open training materials - <https://zenodo.org/communities/dcc-rdm-training-materials/search?page=1&size=20>
- The Open Knowledge Foundation - <https://okfn.org/>

03.5 Open Data tools [1/2] (Zee & Reich, 2018)

Tools for Open Data	Examples
Public data sharing	Open Science Framework (www.OSF.io)
	DANS (https://dans.knaw.nl/en)
	Qualitative Data Repository (https://qdr.syr.edu)
	Repository of data archiving websites (www.re3data.org)
	Dataverse (http://dataverse.org)
Publishing datasets	Nature Scientific Data (https://www.nature.com/sdata/)
	Research Data Journal for the Humanities and Social Sciences (http://www.brill.com/products/online-resources/research-data-journal-humanities-and-social-sciences)
	Journal of Open Psychology Data (https://openpsychologydata.metajnl.com)

03.6 Open Data tools [2/2] (Zee & Reich, 2018)

Tools for Open Data	Examples
Asking for data sharing	Reviewer's Openness Initiative (https://OpennessInitiative.org)
Anonymization	Named entity-based Text Anonymization for Open Science (https://osf.io/w9nhb/) ARX (http://arx.deidentifier.org) Amnesia (https://amnesia.openaire.eu/index.html)
Privacy standards and regulations	U.S. Department of Health & Human Services (https://www.hhs.gov/hipaa/for-professionals/privacy/special-topics/de-identification/index.html#standard) Australian National Data Service (https://www.ands.org.au/working-with-data/sensitive-data/de-identifying-data) European Commission (https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection_en)

04.0 References

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Let's discuss!
Nullius in Verba

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